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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

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EMOTIONAL BURNOUT OF TEACHERS AS A FACTOR INFLUENCING PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: The article presents the results of a theoretical and empirical study of teachers' emotional burnout as a significant socio-psychological factor influencing the effectiveness of their professional activity. Emotional burnout manifests itself in the form of chronic fatigue, decreased motivation, emotional exhaustion, and loss of interest in work, which negatively affects the quality of the educational process. The study also analyzes the main theoretical approaches to understanding the phenomenon of burnout and identifies its key psychological determinants. The empirical part of the research included the assessment of the level of emotional burnout among teachers and the evaluation of the influence of stress-related and interpersonal factors. The results confirmed that a high level of professional stress and a lack of social support contribute to the development of burnout syndrome. In conclusion, the article discusses possible prevention strategies, including the development of stress resistance, the formation of self-regulation skills, and the creation of a favorable socio-psychological climate in educational institutions.

Key words: emotional burnout, teachers, professional activity, stress, psychological well-being, prevention.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada o'qituvchilarning hissiy charchashini ularning kasbiy faoliyati samaradorligiga ta'sir qiluvchi muhim ijtimoiy-psixologik omil sifatida nazariy va empirik o'rganish natijalari keltirilgan. Hissiy charchash surunkali charchoq, motivatsiyaning pasayishi, hissiy charchash, mehnatga qiziqishning yo'qolishi shaklida namoyon bo'ladi, bu esa ta'lim jarayonining sifatiga salbiy ta'sir qiladi. Tadqiqot shuningdek, charchash fenomenini tushunishning asosiy nazariy yondashuvlarini tahlil qiladi va uning asosiy psixologik determinantlarini aniqlaydi. Tadqiqotning empirik qismi o'qituvchilarning hissiy charchash darajasini baholash va stress bilan bog'liq va shaxslararo omillarning ta'sirini baholashni o'z ichiga oladi. Natijalar yuqori darajadagi professional stress va ijtimoiy yordamning etishmasligi charchash sindromining rivojlanishiga yordam berishini tasdiqladi. Xulosa qilib aytganda, maqolada stressga chidamlilikni rivojlantirish, o'z-o'zini boshqarish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish va ta'lim muassasalarida qulay ijtimoiy-psixologik muhitni yaratishni o'z ichiga olgan mumkin bo'lgan oldini olish strategiyalari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: hissiy charchash, o'qituvchilar, kasbiy faoliyat, stress, psixologik farovonlik, oldini olish.

Аннотация: В статье представлены результаты теоретико-эмпирического исследования эмоционального выгорания учителей как значимого социально-психологического фактора, влияющего на эффективность их профессиональной деятельности. Эмоциональное выгорание проявляется в виде хронической усталости, снижения мотивации, эмоционального истощения и потери интереса к работе, что негативно сказывается на качестве образовательного процесса. В исследовании также анализируются основные теоретические подходы к пониманию феномена выгорания и определяются его ключевые психологические детерминанты. Эмпирическая часть исследования включала оценку уровня эмоционального выгорания среди учителей и оценку влияния стрессовых и межличностных факторов. Результаты подтвердили, что высокий уровень профессионального стресса и недостаток социальной поддержки способствуют развитию синдрома выгорания. В заключение в статье обсуждаются возможные стратегии профилактики, включая развитие стрессоустойчивости, формирование навыков саморегуляции и создание благоприятного социально-психологического климата в образовательных учреждениях.

Ключевые слова: эмоциональное выгорание, учителя, профессиональная деятельность, стресс, психологическое благополучие, профилактика.

INTRODUCTION

The professional activity of a teacher is recognized as one of the most complex, demanding, and emotionally charged types of labor. Teaching requires a high level of responsibility, constant cognitive engagement, well-developed communicative competencies, and a high degree of emotional stability. Educators must continuously interact with students, maintain classroom discipline, comply with educational standards, design and implement instruction, and communicate effectively with parents, colleagues, and administrators. Such a multifaceted and dynamic work environment creates an intense psychological load that can gradually exhaust emotional resources and lead to professional burnout.

Contemporary psychological research consistently demonstrates that teaching is among the professions most susceptible to chronic stress. Persistent psycho-emotional overload, the pressure to meet institutional expectations, accountability for students' academic outcomes, and limited time and material resources collectively contribute to heightened stress levels. Over long periods, these stressors may accumulate, resulting in emotional burnout—an adverse psychological condition characterized by emotional and physical exhaustion, declining motivation, reduced enthusiasm toward work, a sense of inefficacy, and emotional distancing from students and colleagues.

The consequences of burnout extend far beyond the individual well-being of teachers. Emotional burnout can significantly reduce professional performance, impair decision-making, increase irritability and conflict within the educational team, and weaken the teacher–student relationship, ultimately affecting the quality of the entire educational process. In severe cases, burnout becomes a barrier to personal development, professional growth, and long-term career sustainability in education.

The urgency of addressing this issue stems from the high prevalence of burnout among educators at all levels—from preschool and primary school teachers to those in secondary and higher education. Numerous studies emphasize that emotional burnout is not merely the result of temporary stress; rather, it is a complex psychophysiological and socio-psychological process shaped by systemic organizational factors, interpersonal dynamics, and individual personality characteristics. This position is supported by the works of both international and national researchers, including C. Maslach and S. Jackson, who introduced the classical model of burnout, as well as V.V. Boyko, N.E. Vodopyanova, and others, who made substantial contributions to the diagnostics and analysis of burnout in professional settings.

Given its multifactorial nature and significant consequences, the study of emotional burnout among teachers represents a priority direction in modern psychological science. A deeper understanding of its mechanisms, determinants, and manifestations enables the development of effective preventative measures, targeted interventions, and psychological support programs. Ultimately, such efforts contribute not only to strengthening teachers' professional resilience and mental well-being but also to improving the overall quality and sustainability of educational systems.

In Uzbekistan today, special attention is being paid to the development of education. The main goal of this process is to improve the quality and effectiveness of education. This task is being accomplished primarily through the wide introduction of modern innovative technologies into the pedagogical process.

Under the conditions of ongoing changes in society, teachers are required not only to have high professional competence but also a strong level of personal self-development and psychological stability. Therefore, in recent years, a number of effective measures have been implemented in various educational institutions of our Republic to ensure the mental well-being of teaching staff, train specialists in the field of occupational psychology, create the necessary conditions for teachers' professional development, and improve the material and technical base.

In particular, as our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev stated, "...we can see that the reforms aimed at transforming social life have begun, first of all, with the education system. The foundation of education and upbringing is the school. And the force that makes a school truly a school is the teachers."

Assigning such responsible duties to teachers also requires ensuring the psychosocial health of pedagogical and academic staff, preventing professional burnout, creating a healthy socio-psychological environment within pedagogical teams, and increasing their resilience to stress through various psychological mechanisms.

Furthermore, in his speeches, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has emphasized the importance of valuing teachers' work and providing them with material and moral support, saying: "We consider our esteemed teachers, dedicated school principals, and honored members of the profession to be the support and reliance of our people." These words reflect the high appreciation of teachers' role in society and their work.

The President's reforms in the field of education are aimed at recognizing teachers' efforts, encouraging them, and strengthening their social status, which in turn is an important factor in preventing emotional exhaustion.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The term "burnout" was introduced by the American psychiatrist H. J. Freudenberger in 1974 to describe a specific psychological state observed in healthy individuals engaged in intensive, emotionally demanding professional interactions with clients or patients. Initially, this phenomenon was understood as a condition of exhaustion and depletion, accompanied by a sense of reduced personal effectiveness, feelings of uselessness, and a noticeable decline in motivation to perform work duties.

In contemporary psychology, emotional burnout is defined as a complex state of mental, emotional, and physical exhaustion that develops as a result of prolonged exposure to psycho-emotional stress. This condition manifests itself through persistent fatigue, decreased energy levels, emotional detachment, and depressive reactions, as well as a diminished ability to perceive positive outcomes of one's own professional efforts. Burnout is considered a distinct psychological state that emerges under the influence of chronic professional stressors and has a destructive impact both on an individual's mental health and on the effectiveness of his or her professional performance ^[12].

A significant contribution to the development of the burnout concept was made by C. Maslach and S. Jackson ^[8], who identified three core components of the syndrome: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization (or cynicism), and reduced personal accomplishment.

1. Emotional exhaustion refers to the feeling of emotional depletion and overwhelming fatigue caused by occupational demands.
2. Depersonalization is expressed in a cynical, detached, and impersonal attitude toward work, clients, patients, or students. On a social level, this manifests as cold, mechanical, and emotionally distant interactions. Over time, these negative attitudes may remain hidden internally but eventually surface through irritation and interpersonal conflicts.
3. Reduced personal accomplishment reflects a decline in one's self-evaluation, decreased confidence in professional competence, and a growing sense of inefficacy and underachievement.
4. Together, these components describe the multidimensional nature of burnout as a severe psychological risk factor affecting professionals working in emotionally intense environments.

A significant contribution to the study of stress factors and the psychological mechanisms of burnout was made by E.P. Ilyin, A.A. Rean, A.B. Leonova, L.M. Mitina, and other researchers. In Russian psychology, interest in the problem of emotional burnout became especially active in the 1990s. V.V. Boyko proposed an original diagnostic method that makes it possible to identify the stages and symptoms of burnout. His method is based on the understanding of burnout as a gradual process that includes the dynamics of psycho-emotional changes in an individual's professional activity ^[4].

N.E. Vodopyanova adapted the C. Maslach burnout inventory for Russian samples and conducted a number of studies among helping professionals, including teachers ^[2].

E.P. Ilyin examined in detail the problem of occupational stress and its impact on the psychophysiological state of a person. In his works, it is emphasized that emotional burnout results from prolonged exposure to stressors as well as insufficient adaptation of the individual to the professional environment ^[5].

A.A. Rean studied issues of motivation, emotional tension, and stress resilience. He noted that burnout is associated not only with external working conditions but also with personality traits of the teacher, such as the level of responsibility, self-esteem, and communication style ^[11].

A.B. Leonova devoted considerable attention to the study of psychological self-regulation mechanisms and coping strategies that can reduce the risk of burnout. Her research demonstrated that a high level of self-control and behavioral flexibility contribute to maintaining professional health [7].

L.M. Mitina worked on the problems of teachers' professional development, studied the dynamics of teachers' emotional states, and identified factors that increase the risk of burnout: high emotional involvement, overload, lack of recognition, and lack of support [9].

Thus, the studies of these authors have made it possible to view the syndrome of emotional burnout as a complex, multifactorial process that includes a combination of external (working conditions, social factors) and internal (personal qualities, style of self-regulation, motivation) causes.

Analysis of the literature shows that contemporary psychological research identifies three main approaches to studying emotional burnout. These approaches explain the emergence of the phenomenon at different levels – individual, interpersonal, and organizational – each of which exists independently while also interacting with the others.

Our review indicates that in Uzbekistan, very few scientific studies have been conducted specifically on the issue of emotional burnout among teachers. However, although the socio-psychological characteristics of emotional burnout itself have not been widely studied, there are scientific works dedicated to the teacher's personality, professional development, professional self-awareness, personality traits typical of teachers, as well as stress and occupational stress.

In particular, the doctoral dissertation by Uzbek scholar D.S. Qarshiyeva titled "Psychological Determinants Influencing the Manifestation of Professional Stress in the Teacher's Personality" examines the psychological factors affecting the emergence of occupational stress in pedagogical staff and their influence on the process of professional burnout. The researcher provides analytical conclusions about the factors contributing to occupational stress among teachers – the socio-psychological environment of the pedagogical team, the teacher's readiness for professional activity, and dynamic aspects associated with years of work experience. She also proposes useful recommendations for overcoming stress and reducing negative emotional experiences [10].

In M. Kaplanova's dissertation "Psychological Characteristics of Teachers in Uzbek Schools," the role of ethnopsychological and social factors influencing the formation of teachers' professional personal qualities is analyzed. The researcher examines the teacher's self-attitude from three perspectives: global self-attitude (the integral "I"), self-respect and autosympathy, and self-evaluation manifested in specific actions toward one's "self," studying their relationship with personality traits from an ethnopsychological standpoint [6].

A.A. Beknazarov analyzed the system of emotional-value relations between teachers and students. A comparative analysis of the emotional-value approach demonstrates its role in ensuring the emotional stability and cognitive coherence of interpersonal interactions between teachers and students [3].

Yu.M. Asadov examined the psychological characteristics that determine the direction of professional and personal growth of general education school teachers within the system of professional development. At this stage, strengthening professional skills and the effectiveness of professional renewal largely depend on personal psychological characteristics [2].

In her dissertation "Psychological Characteristics of Emotional Stability of General Education School Teachers," Sh.X. Abdullayeva investigated teachers' personality, individual psychological and emotional characteristics; the influence of teachers' interpersonal relations with students on the development of emotional instability; teachers' communicative competence; and certain issues related to preventing emotional burnout among teachers in general education schools [1].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The experimental model of the study was designed in such a way that it made it possible to identify, assess, and compare the level of emotional burnout. The empirical data collected during the research were analyzed both quantitatively (statistical analysis) and qualitatively (content analysis). Thus, through the integration of methodological approaches, the emotional burnout of teachers was examined comprehensively, differences between groups were identified, and the study enabled the formulation of practical conclusions.

A total of 60 teachers participated in this study. They were divided into two main groups:

1. 30 preschool education teachers,
2. 30 general education school teachers.

The participants varied in age and work experience; their selection was not random but carried out purposefully in order to cover two main levels of the educational system. This created a solid foundation for comparative analysis.

At this stage, a special diagnostic method was used:

V.V. Boyko's "Emotional Burnout Syndrome Diagnostic Technique."

The questionnaire consists of 84 statements, and the analysis of results is conducted in three stages.

Tension Phase

At this stage, the process of professional burnout begins to form. Tension has a dynamic nature and gradually leads to persistent fatigue and increased psychological vulnerability. Key components of this phase include:

1. Experiencing psychologically traumatic situations: awareness of harmful psychological factors increases, their impact intensifies over time, leading to feelings of hopelessness, anxiety, and loss of control.
2. Dissatisfaction with oneself: a growing sense of inadequacy and reduced satisfaction with one's work and social role, which contributes to early burnout.
3. Feeling trapped ("being in a cage"): the person feels pressured, unable to find solutions, which weakens psychological defense mechanisms.
4. Anxiety and depression: emotional tension connected to professional difficulties leads to chronic worry, hopelessness, and depressive reactions.

Resistance Phase

This phase reflects the individual's psychological defenses against stress. These defenses become noticeable to others, especially students, and may negatively affect relationships.

1. Inadequacy of emotional responses: emotional instability and disproportionate reactions; the individual may ignore or overreact to situations depending on mood.
2. Emotional and moral disorientation: the person justifies inappropriate behavior, becomes more critical, insensitive, or cynical toward others.
3. Expansion of emotional restraint: emotional suppression spreads to personal relationships outside the workplace.
4. Reduction of professional responsibility: a decline in motivation and commitment, especially in professions requiring frequent interpersonal interaction.

Exhaustion Phase

This stage is marked by significant deterioration in health and professional values. The person avoids colleagues and students, and symptoms of professional illness intensify.

1. Emotional deficit: the individual feels unable to provide emotional support or empathy, showing mainly negative reactions.
2. Emotional detachment: emotional withdrawal from professional activity, resulting in indifference and mechanical performance of duties.
3. Depersonalization: loss of interest in others, negative attitudes, and viewing work as meaningless or burdensome.
4. Psychosomatic and psycho-vegetative disorders: emotional stress manifests physically through poor mood, fear, insomnia, unpleasant sensations, or chronic health issues; protective mechanisms weaken and the body becomes more vulnerable.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In our study, we conducted a comparative analysis between the selected groups using the "Emotional Burnout Level Diagnostics" method developed by the psychologist V.V. Boyko. The results obtained through this diagnostic tool served as an important scientific basis for comparing the levels and stages of emotional burnout between the samples, identifying existing differences, and drawing general conclusions.

Below, the results of this analysis are presented in the form of a table for your review:

Table 1: Comparison of Emotional Burnout Symptoms Among Teachers (%)

Stage / Symptom	Preschool Teachers (%)	School Teachers (%)	Comment
TENSION STAGE			
Experiencing psychologically traumatic situations	26.3	20.7	Higher among preschool teachers
Dissatisfaction with oneself	25.3	21.1	Higher among preschool teachers
Feeling trapped or "in a cage"	27.3	20.7	Noticeably higher in preschool teachers
Anxiety and depression	19.3	18.7	Almost no difference
RESISTANCE STAGE			
Inadequacy of emotional reactions	18.2	17.8	No difference
Emotional and moral disorientation	23.9	15.7	Much higher among preschool teachers
Expansion of emotional restraint	19.2	18.8	Similar results
Reduction in professional responsibility	24.1	16.7	Higher among preschool teachers
EXHAUSTION STAGE			
Emotional deficit	19.8	22.6	Higher among school teachers
Emotional detachment	17.2	16.8	No difference
Personal detachment (depersonalization)	22.3	21.7	Practically no difference
Psychosomatic and psycho-vegetative disturbances	13.2	12.8	Low in both groups

According to the results obtained using the "Emotional Burnout Level Diagnostics" method, the symptoms of the Tension phase showed the following tendencies:

A high indicator for the symptom "Experiencing psychologically traumatic situations" was observed among preschool teachers (26.3%), while among general education school teachers this indicator was expressed at a slightly lower level (20.7%).

For the symptom "Dissatisfaction with oneself," preschool teachers again demonstrated a higher score (25.3%) compared to school teachers (21.1%).

The symptom "Feeling trapped (feeling as if being in a cage)" was also more pronounced among preschool teachers (27.3%), whereas the score among school teachers was lower (20.7%).

The symptom "Anxiety and depression" did not show a significant difference between preschool teachers (19.3%) and school teachers (18.7%); both groups demonstrated approximately similar average results.

In the Resistance phase, the following results were identified:

The symptom "Inadequacy of emotional responses" showed no notable difference between preschool teachers (18.2%) and school teachers (17.8%), meaning the results were nearly identical.

For the symptom "Emotional and moral disorientation," preschool teachers demonstrated a much higher indicator (23.9%), while among school teachers this symptom appeared at a lower level (15.7%).

The symptom "Expansion of the domain of emotional restraint" showed no meaningful difference between preschool teachers (19.2%) and school teachers (18.8%); both groups displayed similar average scores.

For the scale "Reduction of professional responsibility," preschool teachers showed a higher indicator (24.1%), whereas school teachers demonstrated a lower level (16.7%).

In the Exhaustion phase, the following symptom scores were identified:

For the symptom "Emotional deficit," preschool teachers showed a lower indicator (19.8%), while school teachers demonstrated a higher score (22.6%).

Regarding "Emotional detachment," there was no noticeable difference between preschool (17.2%) and school teachers (16.8%), showing approximately equal results.

The symptom "Personal detachment or depersonalization" also did not reveal any significant differences: preschool teachers scored 22.3%, while school teachers scored 21.7%, indicating nearly identical average results.

For "Psychosomatic and psycho-vegetative disorders," no significant difference was observed: the indicator was low among both preschool teachers (13.2%) and school teachers (12.8%).

The analysis of the data obtained through the "Emotional Burnout Level Diagnostics" method reveals distinct patterns in the formation of burnout among preschool teachers compared to general education school

teachers. These patterns highlight differences in emotional load, professional challenges, and the nature of interpersonal interactions within each educational setting.

1. Tension Phase

The Tension phase reflects the initial psychological reactions to prolonged stress. The results indicate that preschool teachers experience significantly higher emotional strain than school teachers.

1. Experiencing psychologically traumatic situations and feeling trapped are notably more pronounced among preschool teachers. This suggests that the emotionally charged and physically demanding nature of working with very young children may contribute to a heightened sense of being overwhelmed or constrained.
2. Dissatisfaction with oneself is also more common among preschool educators, indicating increased vulnerability to self-criticism, possibly due to the constant emotional involvement required in preschool settings.
3. The symptom anxiety and depression demonstrated nearly equal results in both groups, suggesting that general emotional disturbances may be linked to the broader teaching profession rather than to specific work conditions.

Overall, the Tension phase profiles indicate that preschool teachers are more emotionally reactive to stressors, which may create a stronger foundation for subsequent burnout phases.

2. Resistance Phase

This phase reflects the development of psychological defenses aimed at coping with ongoing stress.

1. The similarity in the symptom inadequacy of emotional responses suggests that both groups attempt to regulate their emotions but may struggle equally when stress exceeds their coping capacity.
2. Emotional and moral disorientation is substantially higher among preschool teachers, pointing to possible conflicts between personal values and daily professional demands. This may arise from the intensive emotional caregiving expected in early childhood education.
3. No meaningful differences were observed in the expansion of emotional restraint, indicating that both groups similarly rely on emotional suppression as a coping strategy.
4. A higher rate of reduction in professional responsibility among preschool teachers may signal growing emotional fatigue, avoidance behaviors, or a decline in motivation – all markers of progressing burnout.

Taken together, the data show that preschool teachers more frequently transition into maladaptive coping patterns, suggesting they may be at higher risk for developing more severe forms of burnout.

3. Exhaustion Phase

The Exhaustion phase captures deep emotional, cognitive, and physical depletion.

1. Emotional deficit was higher among school teachers, suggesting that despite experiencing lower initial tension, they may ultimately lose more emotional energy over time. This could reflect the cumulative challenges of classroom management, academic pressure, and interactions with older students and parents.
2. Emotional detachment and personal depersonalization showed no significant group differences, indicating that by the exhaustion stage, both preschool and school teachers reach similarly high levels of emotional distancing and decreased personal involvement in their work.
3. Psychosomatic and psycho-vegetative disorders remained low in both groups, suggesting that while emotional and cognitive symptoms of burnout are evident, the somatic manifestations are not yet pronounced.

Overall, the Exhaustion phase results indicate that both groups of teachers ultimately reach comparable levels of deep emotional depletion, even though preschool teachers show higher vulnerability at earlier stages.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The present study provides a comprehensive analysis of emotional burnout among teachers working in preschool and general education settings. Using V. Boyko's diagnostic framework, the research identified both shared and distinct patterns of emotional exhaustion across professional groups. The results demonstrate that preschool teachers exhibit higher levels of tension-related symptoms, including psychological traumatic experiences, dissatisfaction with themselves, and a persistent sense of emotional confinement. These findings suggest that the emotional demands of early childhood education place a considerable burden on teachers, increasing their vulnerability to stress and burnout.

At the same time, several indicators—such as emotional alienation, depersonalization, psychosomatic reactions, and anxiety—were similar across both groups, highlighting that certain aspects of burnout are inherent to

the teaching profession as a whole. These common symptoms point to systemic challenges within the educational environment, such as intensive workload, emotional labor, and insufficient institutional support.

The differences identified between the groups underscore the importance of considering the specific professional context when developing preventive and corrective interventions. Preschool educators may benefit from targeted programs aimed at emotional regulation, stress management, and improving professional self-efficacy. General education teachers, on the other hand, require support that addresses chronic stress accumulation and behavioral challenges associated with older students.

Overall, the study confirms that emotional burnout is a multifactorial phenomenon shaped by professional responsibilities, emotional demands, and individual coping capacities. The findings emphasize the need for comprehensive institutional measures that promote teacher well-being, strengthen psychological resilience, and reduce occupational stress. Implementing such strategies is essential for enhancing the quality of the educational process and fostering a healthier, more sustainable professional environment for teachers at all levels.

Recommendations. To prevent and reduce emotional burnout among teachers, the following measures are recommended:

Psychological Support Programs

- Implement regular psychological counseling sessions for teachers.
- Establish school-based mental health centers offering preventive and corrective support.

Professional Development on Stress Management

- Conduct training on coping strategies, emotional regulation, and conflict management.
- Provide workshops on mindfulness, relaxation techniques, and self-reflection practices.

Improving Work Conditions

- Ensure a balanced workload by reducing unnecessary administrative tasks.
- Create supportive and collaborative professional environments within pedagogical teams.

Strengthening Social and Organizational Support

- Enhance communication between administration and teachers.
- Encourage peer-support groups where educators can share experiences and find mutual understanding.

Enhancing Teachers' Professional Identity and Motivation

- Increase recognition and acknowledgment of teachers' efforts.
- Provide opportunities for career growth, autonomy, and creative professional activity.

Monitoring Burnout Levels

- Conduct regular diagnostic assessments using standardized psychological tools.
- Develop individualized intervention plans for teachers showing early signs of burnout.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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